

STRANGELY FAMILIAR

Dismantling a clustered care complex into separate dwellings for people with mental disabilities in Monnikenheide-Spectrum

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UR architects

Photography new situation Michiel De Cleene

(a) The original Monnikenbos (completed in 1980)

UR architects was commissioned to redesign the clustered Monnikenbos after winning a limited competition in 2012 to reimagine portions of the residential care centre of Monnikenheide-Spectrum in the municipality of Zoersel. While the architectural project was delivered in 2020, the landscape project is still in progress.

For more information on the different projects in Monnikenheide see: Gideon Boie (ed.), Sofie De Caigny, Kurt Deruyter (photography), Fredie Floré, Vjera Sleutel, Thomas Vanderveken, Heleen Verheyden and Erik Wieërs, *Living in Monnikenheide: Care, Inclusion and Architecture* (Antwerp: Flanders Architecture Institute, 2023).

For previous research-by-design on psychiatric care sites by UR see: *The Psychiatric Asylum Dismantled* (The Netherlands, 2009), commissioned by the Dutch Creative Industries Fund and *The Future of the Asylum* (Belgium, 2012), commissioned by the Flanders Architecture Institute.

*Remembering or forgetting is doing gardener's work,
selecting, pruning. Memories are like plants: there are those
that need to be quickly eliminated in order to help the others
burgeon, transform, flower.*

Marc Augé, *Oblivion*, 2004

The adaptive reuse of Monnikenbos is akin to a game of hide-and-seek with the memories of the settlement. Working with its existing qualities becomes a play with varying degrees of familiarity and estrangement. Rather than fetishising the remaining structure as a recognisable remnant, it continues to build on material fragments or architectural features in dialogue with the original. This visual essay documents the before and after of the project. The interaction between old and new portrays the 'selecting and pruning' of spatial recollections, between resemblance and distortion, but always contextualising places in time. At first glance, the images form a subtle narrative of the architectural transformation of atmospheres from within. On closer inspection, however, they reveal a more patient transformation: after the residents, the landscape has also moved back in. Having originally turned its back on the surrounding forest, the new Monnikenbos finally lives up to its name by activating and cultivating it.

(b) Situation plan and landscape

(a)

(b) Section and floor plan

(a) Before and after schemes show the transformation of the closed cluster into an open settlement with upgraded free-standing dwellings.

(b) The section adds a floor and raises the roof.

The floor plan maintains a close relationship with the original single-storey layout, mainly enlarging the existing interiors of the residential units.

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(c) The project retains the residential units while further transforming the character from institutional to domestic.

The starting point was to rethink the role of the indoor agora, replacing it with an informal courtyard.

The resulting new envelope redefines the exterior and significantly changes the appearance of the project.

(d) Detailed section

CHAPTER 5 RE-PRESENTATIONS

(a)

(b)

(c)

(a, b) The agora is turned inside out, while the position of the front doors is maintained.

They are (re)activated as real entrances facing each other.

The courtyard becomes informal, permeable and green.

The play of entrances and passages between the houses transforms it into a meeting place.

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(c, d) Each bedroom on the ground floor extends outwards with a veranda and direct access to the outside.

Fragments of the old façade have been retained on the inside to preserve and shelter the sleeping area.

The veranda floor becomes part of the garden, creating extra light and space for play.

(d)

CHAPTER 5 RE-PRESENTATIONS

(a, b) The corridors are no longer dead-ends but now connect the two living rooms at either end of each dwelling.

The corridors thus become part of a continuous, meandering communal space that also connects to the outside.

Glazed ceilings provide natural light and visual contact with the mature wooded surroundings.

(a)

(b)

(c)

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(d)

(c, d) The shade of the trees extends into the room.

A staircase leads to the new first floor for the more independent members of the group.

Upstairs, an opening in the wall allows views back into the space and beyond.

The open space and the wooden furniture bring the residents together.

CHAPTER 5 RE-PRESENTATIONS

(a)

(b)

(c)

(a, b) Although the settlement is different, the relationship with the environment remains the same.

The low vegetation surrounds the houses, defines the gardens and provides a transition to the forest.

Each bedroom has a door to the outside, activating the garden as an extension of the living space.

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(c, d) While the dining room near the entrance connects to the courtyard, the second living room looks outwards.

As a break-out room with a more leisurely character, it allows for different configurations and activities.

As it faces the landscape, it offers more relaxation and deeper views of the surroundings.

(d)

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